

A CORPUS-BASED ANALYSIS OF ADVERBIAL CLAUSES IN LITERARY TEXTS

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ABSTRACT

Adverbial clauses in literary texts represent a semantically diverse and challenging class of subordinate clauses. They are crucial in creating a coherent discourse and a prominent feature, especially in written texts. This study aimed to examine and analyze the linguistic functions of adverbial clauses in literary texts. It was a qualitative study that involved a linguistic analysis of the corpus. It quantified the frequency with which adverbial clauses were used in the corpus and how they were employed by assessing their grammatical categories and positions. Analysis revealed that adverbial clauses typically alter verbs but can also modify adjectives and adverbs. From the corpus's concordance lines, adverbial clauses do not have a fixed location in the sentence. They can be put at a sentence's beginning, middle, or conclusion without affecting its grammatical meaning. The findings suggested that adverbial clauses are prevalent in grammatical and semantic discourse. As a research product, a learning activity sheet was created to help students improve their understanding of adverbial clauses. Future scholars are also encouraged to perform a broader study of corpus linguistics.

Keywords: *Adverbial clauses, Corpus, Corpus linguistics, Grammatical categories, Literary texts*

INTRODUCTION

Many languages feature methods by which one sentence can similarly change another to how an adverb modifies a proposition. This is known as clause modification. Adverb clauses, like adverbs, which are single words or phrases, can be named and

categorized according to their semantic roles in a sentence or paragraph. An adverbial clause does not function as an essential part of a sentence. It is only an adjunct or an add-on. Hence, it can be removed from the main clause without affecting the sentence's grammatical sense. However, using an adverbial clause in a sentence is a good way to add important, descriptive detail and information to your writing. Single-word adverbs and adverbial clauses have no fixed position in the sentence. They can be placed at the beginning of a sentence, immediately before or after the words they modify depending on where it sounds best. Thus, knowing its proper use and functions leads to informative and meaningful writing.

When it comes to relationships between clauses, there is little doubt that there is a continuum. A discussion of how clauses might be coupled on this continuum will be discussed further (Lehmann, 1988). We can distinguish three types of subordinate clauses based on the assumption that the "subordinate" end of this continuum includes clauses that are grammatically dependent on another clause or some element in another clause: those that serve as complements for nouns, those that serve as relative clauses for nouns, and those that serve as *enti* clauses for verb phrases or *enti* (also known as adverbial clauses). When it comes to these three sorts of clauses, complement clauses, and relative clauses are most often used to indicate embedding structure at the subordinate end of the continuum, i.e., one clause inside another and a sentence within a noun phrase, respectively. Due to the fact that they are related to the main sentence in its whole, adverbial clauses are considered to be (hypotactic) clauses combining the main clause rather than independent clauses (Matthiessen & Thompson, 1988). Recent work by Wang (2002) breaks fresh ground in studying adverbial clauses by adopting a corpus-based approach. Because it is often difficult to make strong generalizations about grammatical constructions when they occur too infrequently, most researchers have found it profitable to investigate constructions that occur relatively frequently to investigate the use and structure of grammatical construction (Meyer, 1994).

These studies of adverbial clauses concentrated on the discourse functions of just a few semantic classes of the adverbial clauses (conditional, temporal, and causal adverb clauses) and relied on spoken corpora. The discourse roles of adverbial clauses have been studied in great depth, and the findings of this research all point to the conclusion that the initial adverbial clauses establish a framework for the subsequent clauses in the sentence. The last adverbial clauses, on the other hand, were exclusively used to modify the previous main phrase. More research, however, is needed to give an in-depth analysis of all the potential semantic types of adverbial clauses. This analysis was conducted using a large amount of written corpus data.

Adverbial clauses were identified from a corpus of literary texts in the English 10 textbooks. Generating these words from a corpus of literary texts was made more comfortable using different corpus-linguistic software that can automatically search terms that occur most frequently in the compiled corpus. These words were presented on a computer screen to decrease their frequency of occurrence; that is, the first word on screen had the most incidents in the corpus.

The researchers decided what linguistic analysis should be made depending on her interest in the identified adverbial clauses. It chose a content analysis of adverbial clauses, considering that many of her students had difficulty identifying even adverbs and adverbial clauses in sentences from literary texts. A corpus-based study was carried out, allowing for the analysis of a large amount of data to provide more trustworthy hypotheses (Baker, 2006). AntConc 3.5.8 corpus software was used to analyze corpus data and determine the frequency of adverbial phrases as reflected by particular attributes (Oshima & Hogue, 2007; Zemaxh & Rumisek, 2003).

The calculation revealed the usage of adverbial clauses and the sequence of words that follow them. As a result, the use of adverbial clauses in literary growth impacts how it should be taught in the classroom.

The researchers adopted a theoretically informed corpus-based approach in adverbial clauses, as this approach is associated with patterns and contextual factors (Quintero, 2002). These studies were based on corpus evidence without using a theoretical framework (Greenbaum, 1973; Thompson & Longacare, 1985), or they were based on a theory formed by introspections at the expense of a wealth of language data that can be obtained from a corpus (Comrie, 1986; Givon, 1993; Bhatt & Pancheva, 2001).

The researchers' primary purpose of this study was to determine the different uses of adverbial clauses in sentences through literary texts from Grade 10 textbooks. The variety of adverbial clauses used in the texts differed depending on the context and messages it wanted to convey. Further, this qualitative study explained how students identified and used adverbial clauses in writing, speaking, and reading by analyzing literary texts. Moreover, this study aimed to achieve a corpus-based, wide-ranging, theoretically informed analysis of all semantic types of adverbial clauses from literary texts. Finally, the research output of this study was to design a Learning Activity Sheet about adverbial clauses to address the needs of students in learning the lesson. This tool served as a supplement to deepen students' understanding of adverbial clauses using easier language.

Research Questions

1. What parts of speech are modified by the adverbial clauses introduced by *as*, *if*, *when*, *where*, and *because*?
2. What position within the sentences in the corpus are occupied by these adverbial clauses?
3. What learning activity sheet on adverbial clauses be designed based on the compiled corpus?

METHODOLOGY

Research Instrument

The main instrument of this study was the literary texts taken from English 10 textbooks used by public and private schools. Ninety-two literary texts were in the corpus, and the frequency analysis of adverbial clauses was calculated by AntConc 3.5.8 corpus software. AntConc is open-access (free to download) corpus analysis software that allows users to analyze large amounts of text and produce data based on aspects such as frequency. It also enables users to provide concordance lines for qualitative data analysis.

Source of Language Data

The study used a corpus of ninety-two (92) literary texts from Grade 10 English books currently used by DepEd and private schools. The literary texts were taken from one DepEd book and four K–12 compliant books from private schools, namely Celebrating Diversity through World Literature (DepEd), Essential English Worktext in Literature and Language (REX), English Communication Arts and Skills through World Literature (PHOENIX), English Across Continents (DIWA), and The Global Village (SIBS). The research investigation covered all the texts in each literary text that contain adverbial clauses. This study analyzed corpus data using qualitative content analysis.

Genre	No. of Literary Texts	Number of Words
Short Stories	80	132, 947
Novels	12	25, 842
	Total	158, 789

Research Design

This study used a qualitative research design involving a linguistic corpus analysis. Regarding the study design, the researchers analyzed the literary texts qualitatively. The researchers employed content analysis in this study because the adverbial clauses were selected from a corpus of ninety-two (92) literary texts. The data of adverbial clauses with the selected subordinating conjunctions from the corpus must be evaluated. Following that, the researchers provided an interpretation of the data analysis results. The content analysis method dealt with current records or contents as the data's sources of information. The information about adverbial clauses from the corpus was accurate. Hence, the study used content analysis, and the adverbial clauses were also analyzed using the corpus linguistics approach in research since this study dealt with the grammatical structures of sentences.

Data Gathering Procedure

A corpus-based analysis was carried out to examine a large amount of data and produce a more trustworthy generalization (Baker, 2006). This study's data-gathering phase started with identifying ninety-two literary texts from Grade 10 English books used by DepEd schools and four other English textbooks used by private schools. The books' choice and texts included in the corpus were based on the fact that the researchers taught Grade 10 English, and the literary texts frequently used adverbial clauses since this is one of the book's learning competencies. Moreover, the literary texts were easy and interesting to read, which students can apply to their future academic writing.

Since this study was conducted using content analysis, the 92 corpus were classified according to genre (short stories and novels). Each corpus underwent the weeding-out process to ensure a smooth flow when running the AntConc software. In the process of weeding or building the corpus, there were signs, symbols, or punctuation marks excluded, like the apostrophe ('), the apostrophe in s ('s), and quotation marks ("") since the software does not recognize these signs. After the weeding process, each corpus from the Word document format was converted to plain text in one folder to prepare for running or processing the data for the software.

After that, the researchers looked for adverbial clauses with subordinating conjunctions in the sentence. According to the concordance lines from the corpus, the researcher was able to identify the top five subordinating conjunctions (when, as, whether, where, and why), which were then employed in the analytic process.

Data Analysis

Several general stages were followed when conducting qualitative research to examine the data. According to Ary et al. (2010), the first stage in interpreting qualitative data is to organize the data into a meaningful structure. In this step, the researchers gathered descriptive data from the corpus of English 10 textbooks, which included 92 literary texts that were analyzed according to the types and functions of adverbial clauses. In this step, the researchers collected descriptive data from the corpus of English 10 textbooks, which included 92 literary texts that were analyzed according to the types and functions of adverbial clauses. The information was organized in a table. The researchers used the classification to tally the frequency of occurrences of the top five subordinating conjunctions (*when, as, if, where, and because*), which resulted in a total frequency of 1023 instances of the subordinating conjunctions.

However, upon analyzing the functions of adverbial clauses, there were 972 total occurrences according to the grammatical functions of adverbial clauses. The second step was categorizing the data into smaller categories through a classification procedure. For the researchers, it was necessary to understand the grammatical categories of adverbial clauses and their placement in the phrase. The researchers could focus on the clause pattern that occurred by selecting the top five subordinating conjunctions. This study needed 219 frequency of *as*, 205 frequency of *if*, 323 frequency of *when*, 130

frequency of where, and 95 frequency of because to obtain 972 frequency of subordinating conjunctions in adverbial clauses from the corpus. Following data collection, the researchers restricted the data to only those grammatical types and placements of adverbial clauses.

The result was explained descriptively to determine its clear implications for how adverbial clauses were used appropriately and adequately in literary texts.

RESULTS

The exploration of adverbial clauses in literary works, as well as the interpretation of their linguistic functions based on the corpus, are presented in this study. The study results conveyed that adverbial clauses are introduced by subordinating conjunctions that modify a verb, an adjective, and other adverbs. However, from the corpus analysis, modifying adverbial clauses as a verb occurred many times, and adjectives and adverbs were frequently modified. Furthermore, adverbial clauses appeared in no fixed position. To address the needs of learners in learning adverbial clauses, a Learning Activity Sheet was designed as the research output of this corpus study.

DISCUSSION

Based on analyzing the corpus of literary texts introduced by the subordinating conjunctions as, if, when, where, and because, adverbial clauses modified verbs, adjectives, and other adverbs. From the corpus analysis, adverbial clauses modifying as a verb occurred 844 times, an adjective occurred 50 times, and an adverb occurred 38 times. The study generated a total frequency of 972 of these subordinating conjunctions from the corpus.

Thus, based on the corpus analysis, the adverbial clauses appeared in the sentence's front position, middle position, and end position. According to the position of adverbial clauses with their subordinating conjunctions, there were 321 occurrences in the front position. In comparison, 210 occurrences were in the middle position, and the highest was in the end position with 441 occurrences. From the corpus analysis, adverbial clauses have no fixed position in the sentence according to each of the subordinating conjunctions used. When used as a clause, it can be used at the beginning, middle, or end of a statement. This illustrates that the placement of an adverbial phrase in a sentence, whether at the beginning, middle, or conclusion, does not impact or change the meaning of the sentence.

The research result of this corpus study was the development of a learning activity sheet that might assist teachers in overcoming the challenge of the limited time available to spend with each student while also enabling them to improve students' acquisition of knowledge and skills. Understanding prior information, learning outcomes, and the learning process can all be gained through this analysis. At the same time, this application

can help students keep track of their progress while they learn in this new, everyday environment.

Conclusions

The researchers concluded that adverbial clauses do not always modify verbs from the main clause but sometimes modify adjectives and adverbs. Adverbial clauses always start with a subordinating conjunction and must connect to the main clause to make sense and create a complete sentence. To teach students techniques for writing adverbial clauses, they should also know how subordinating conjunctions play an important part in constructing these clauses since these conjunctions serve as a clue to begin and identify adverbial clauses in sentences. The study also concluded that the placement or position of adverbial clauses does not change the meaning of a sentence.

In general, the researchers realized the importance of learning the use of adverbial clauses in writing and speaking. When students understand how to recognize different types of clauses and feel confident using adverbial clauses in their writing, we will see drastic differences in the quality and voice of our students' work. The common, simplistic sentences suddenly transform into something much more eloquent by implementing these clauses.

With the results from the corpus, to provide further learning or supplemental learning activities to students, a learning activity sheet was developed to support and promote students' learning and enhance students' acquisition of knowledge and skills. These simplified activities surely help students master the lesson using adverbial clauses since the lesson discussions and activities in the modules (book) were insufficient to sustain the learning.

Recommendations

This study brings advantages for readers who experienced difficulty learning adverbs and adverbial clauses. With this study, they may understand adverbial clauses' functions, positions, and nature. To ensure quality education, this study recommends that the books used by the public schools should be appropriately reviewed, and the curriculum should adequately cover adverbs in detail so that the students can understand adverbs and adverbial clauses thoroughly. In addition, future scholars are encouraged to perform broader research on corpus linguistics to expand their knowledge. Even though a corpus is being used to investigate words' frequency and grammatical focus, future researchers could use the corpus to explore other phenomena in linguistic studies. Furthermore, different corpora can be used by future researchers to undertake corpus-based analysis.

Additionally, English teachers are encouraged to simplify lessons from books and be resourceful in looking for materials for students' learning processes because more books provide better learning. Hence, copies of this study may be shared with the language teachers to encourage them to do better in teaching the language, know the

importance of corpus-based studies, and master the lessons in English to ensure the quality of learning we aim for.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The ethical criteria for this study were based on the Intellectual Property Code of the Philippines, prescribed by Republic Act No. 8293, which also established the Intellectual Property Office and specified its powers and functions, among other things. For Section 187 of Chapter 8 of copyright limitations, "reproduction of a published work" is defined as "the private reproduction of a published work, in a single copy, made by a natural person solely for research and private study, without reference to any particular purpose, and subject to the provisions of subsection 187.2."

The researchers' data collection was based on the literary texts from English Grade 10 textbooks that DepEd and private schools used. In collecting the corpus, the researcher ensured that these data must be acknowledged and recognized by stating the title and publishing company of each textbook used to gather the data. The title and publishing company of the textbooks were found in the source of language data for this study.

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